

Influence of weather factors on light trap catches of yellow stem borer (YSB)

S. Ramakrishnan and M. S. Venugopal,
Horticultural Research Station, Tamil Nadu
G.D. Naidu Agricultural University,
Udhagamandalam 643001, Tamil Nadu, India

Light trap catches of YSB were recorded for a year (1988-89) using three light traps: a local bamboo light trap with an ordinary incandescent 40-watt bulb (LBL-T 40 W) and two modified Robinson light traps, one with a 125-watt mercury vapor lamp (MRL-T 125 W) and the other with a 200-watt incandescent bulb (MRL-T 200 W). Traps were

Multiple regression between YSB catches in different light traps and weather parameters^a at RRS, Tirur.

Trap	Multiple regression equation	R ²
LBL-T 40 W	93.07197 + 0.05877x ₁ - 0.86273x ₂ - 0.31734x ₃ - 0.83071x ₄	0.34962
MRL-T 125 W	88.30018 - 1.06939x ₁ - 0.06741x ₂ - 0.56557x ₃ - 0.50919x ₄	0.33739
MRL-T 200 W	201.77216 - 1.69501x ₁ - 0.89709x ₂ - 0.92290x ₃ - 1.28137x ₄	0.30677
LBL-T 40 W + MRL-T 125 W + MRL-T 200 W	356.64844 - 2.18550x ₁ - 1.98679x ₂ - 1.86689x ₃ - 2.46711x ₄	0.32607

^ax₁ = maximum temperature, x₂ = minimum temperature, x₃ = rainfall, x₄ = relative humidity.

installed 100 m apart at the Rice Research Station (RRS), Tirur.

Multiple regression analysis was used to study the influence of weather elements on YSB catches. Mean weather parameters for the corresponding week were compared with light trap catches.

The regression equation explained 35% of the variation in LBL-T 40 W, 33.7% in MRL-T 125 W, and 30.7% in MRL-T 200 W, and 32.6% in the three traps collectively (see table). Weather factors did not significantly contribute to the trap catches, irrespective of light trap design. □

Integrated pest management—other pests

Use of ducks to control golden apple snail *Ampullarius (Pomacea) canaliculata* in irrigated rice

P. C. Pantua, S. V. Mercado, F. O. Lanting,
and E. B. Nuevo, Centralized Research Farm,
IRRI

The golden apple snail was introduced in the Philippines as a source of food and income in the early 1980s. It spread into rice and now infests 400,000 ha. Farmers controlled the pest with chemical molluscicides until use was suspended because of safety and environmental concerns.

Some Filipino farmers have used ducks (an important income source) to control the golden apple snail in rice. But no previous studies had documented the efficacy of ducks in suppressing snails or the stocking density needed for good results.

We conducted a field experiment on the IRRI farm to determine how many ducks are needed to control snails in 1 ha of irrigated rice during the dry season (May 1991). Snails were up to 3 cm in diameter and were not fully grown.

The 10- × 10-m experimental plots were irrigated. Snails were counted 2 d later in five 1-m quadrats to estimate populations. Ducks (0, 2, 4, 8, 16, and 32/plot) were then introduced.

Treatments were replicated five times. Ducks remained in the plots for 2 d (8 h/d) and were then removed. Rice variety IR72 (12 d old) was transplanted the next day.

Snail populations were estimated again for each plot at 7 d after transplant-

ing using the same procedure. Rice was examined for snail damage.

Two ducks/plot (200/ha) significantly reduced both the snail population (Table 1) and damage to rice, with four or more per plot increasing effectiveness (Table 2). Results show that ducks are a potential alternative to chemical molluscicides in controlling the golden apple snail. □

Table 1. Efficiency of different duck densities in reducing snail populations in irrigated rice. IRRI, May 1991.

Duck density/plot	Snail control (%) in 7 d
0	13.4 b
2	89.2 a
4	77.2 a
8	91.4 a
16	97.2 a
32	95.8 a

^aMeans with a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test (CV = 29%).

Table 2. Snail damage in irrigated rice at 7 d after transplanting with different densities of ducks, IRRI, May 1991.

Duck density/plot	Snail-damaged rice hills ^a (no./100 m ²)
0	17.4 c
2	8.2 bc
4	6.6 b
8	5.2 b
16	2.0 a
32	4.0 b

^aMeans with a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with upland rice in Sitiung, West Sumatra, Indonesia

J. C. Prot, IRRI; M. Herman, Bogor
Research Institute for Food Crops; and A.
Ahmadin, Sukarami Agricultural Research
Institute for Food Crops (SARIF) Indonesia

We conducted a preliminary survey to identify the major plant parasitic

nematodes in upland rice in Sitiung. Deforestation and opening agricultural land at the site began 15 yr ago; upland rice has been cultivated for 13 yr.

We collected 141 soil and root samples of a second upland rice crop, 1 yr after deforestation, at the SARIF experimental station in Sitiung (new fields = NF), and of 13-yr-old continuously cropped upland ricefields (old fields = OF). The third set was from